

Syntheses of Furano Compounds: Part XXX. A Synthesis of α -Anhydro-*o*-tetramethylhaematoxylone

J. N. Chatterjea, K. D. Banerji and N. M. Sahay

An unambiguous synthesis of α -anhydro-*o*-tetramethylhaematoxylone (II) and the related *ortho* quinone (IV) is described. Experiments on the synthesis of the isomeric 6:7 dimethoxy 4'-hydroxy 6':7'-dimethoxynaphtho (2':1'—2:3) coumarone (XVI) are also described.

O-Tetramethylhaematoxylin on oxidation with chromic acid gives *o*-tetramethylhaematoxylone (I)² which is readily transformed into α -anhydro-*o*-tetramethylhaematoxylone (II) by intramolecular aldol condensation followed by elimination of water with the help of dilute alkali³. The acetate (III) is directly obtained⁴ by the action of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride on (I). Recently O. Dann and H. Hofmann⁵ have reported a synthesis of this acetate in course of their elegant work on the total synthesis of *dl*-haematoxylin. In this paper we report a different synthesis of (II) and the related *ortho*-quinone (IV).

1. Part XXIX, J. N. Chatterjea, S. N. P. Gupta and V. N. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 205.
2. Pfeiffer, Haack and Willems, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 295; Pfeiffer, Angern, Haack and Willems, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 839.
3. W. H. Perkin (Jr.) and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (London) 1908, **93**, 502.
4. W. H. Parkin (Jr.), *J. Chem. Soc.* (London), 1902, **81**, 1058; V. Kostanecki and A. Rost, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2203.
5. O. Dann and H. Hofmann, *Chem. Ber.*, 1965, **98**, 1998.

V, R=H

VI, R=CH₂COCH₃VII, R=CH₂COOEtVIII, R=COCH₃

IX, R=COOH

X, R=CH₂CONH₂XI, R=CH₂COOH

In our experiments directed towards the synthesis of (II) we prepared the benzophenone (V) by Friedel-Crafts reaction of veratroyl chloride with 1,2,3-trimethoxybenzene in carbon disulphide. This was next condensed with bromoacetone to give (VI) which was cyclised to the coumarone (VIII) by alkali. All attempts to effect a photochemically induced bromination⁶ of the side chain (CO-CH₃ → COCH₂Br) failed; the only product isolable was the nuclear bromination product (VIII, Br at position 5) and in the event the projected synthesis of (II) by intramolecular Friedel-Crafts cyclisation⁷ of the expected bromo-ketone could not be brought about.

XII, R=H, R'=COOEt

XIII, R=CH₂COOH, R'=COOH

XIV, R=COOH

XV, R=CH₂COOH

XVI

6. cf. K. W. Bentley and R. Robinson, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 2, p.11.7. A. Collet, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1897, 17, 506; J. P. Mason and L. I. Terry, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1622.

Next, Friedel-Crafts reaction of the acid chloride derived from the half-ester of *m*-hemipinic acid with 1,2,3-trimethoxybenzene in anhydrous ether⁸ gave (XII) under carefully controlled conditions. This was next condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the product hydrolysed to give haematoxylinic acid (XIII). This on treatment with boiling acetic anhydride containing sodium acetate gave 3-(2'-carboxy-4': 5'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxy coumarone ((XIV) from which the acetic acid (XV) was prepared by Arndt-Eistert synthesis. Cyclisation of this acid with sulphuric acid gave (II) which showed reactions of a β -naphthol and is apparently identical in properties with that recorded for the naturally derived product⁹. The derived acetate (III) was identical with a specimen kindly placed at our disposal by Prof. O. Dann. On oxidation with potassium nitrosodisulphonate¹⁰ in aqueous acetone this β -naphthol readily gave the *ortho*-quinone (IV) prepared earlier by Perkin and Robinson¹¹ from (II) by nitration, reduction and oxidation. This quinone has now been characterised by the preparation of a quinoxalin derivative by condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine.

Experiments were also carried out to synthesise the isomeric α -naphthol (XVI), a derivative of 4-hydroxy-naphtho (2':1'-2:3) coumarone (*cf.* Ref. 9). The phenol (V) on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate gave the phenoxy ester (VII) which was cyclised and then hydrolysed to the coumarilic acid (IX). Arndt-Eistert homologation gave the derived amide (X) in a crystalline condition although the corresponding acid (XI) failed to crystallise. The acid on treatment with phosphoric anhydride in benzene gave a bicarbonate insoluble product which also could not be induced to crystallise. The product (expected to be XVI) however did not show any colour reaction with chloroform and alkali but gave a positive ferric reaction. The i.r. spectrum revealed a ketonic band at 1740 cm^{-1} and this necessitates further investigation of the nature of the compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were determined in KBr pellet in Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, model 237. The N.M.R. spectra were determined in CDCl_3 in a Varian A-60 apparatus.

2-Hydroxy-3:4:3':4'-tetramethoxybenzophenone(V).—To a mixture of veratroyl chloride (20.0 g.) and trimethylpyrogallol (17.0 g.) in carbon disulphide (80. ml) was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (27.0 g.). After the initial reaction had subsided, the mixture was refluxed vigorously on water bath for 7 hrs. Carbon disulphide was then distilled off and the residue decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid and the resulting solid collected and crystallised from ethanol. The ketone (11.0 g.) which separated in yellowish needles, m.p. 121-22° giving a positive ferric reaction, was soluble in dilute alkali solution. (ν max. 1620 cm^{-1}). The N.M.R. spectrum showed 12 protons (4 OMe) at 6.0 τ and aromatic protons at 2.34—3.46 τ . (Found: C, 64.21; H, 5.61. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 64.14; H, 5.70%).

It gave a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 206-207°; from ethanol. (Found: N, 11.35. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_9\text{N}_4$ requires, N, 11.24%).

8. *cf.* J. N. Chatterjya and S. K. Roy, *Jour. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 155.

9. The synthetic route is similar to that employed by P. C. Johnson and A. Robertson, *J. Chem., Soc.* (London) 1950, 2331 in their synthesis of α -anhydro-*o*-trimethylbrazilone.

10. T. J. King and G. Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (London), 1961, 5090.

11. W. H. Perkin (Jr.) and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (London), 1909, **95**, 399.

2-Acetyl-3-(3':4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxycoumarone (VIII).—A mixture of the foregoing phenol (3.2 g.), bromoacetone (1.1 ml.) and potassium carbonate (14.0 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed for 18 hrs. The mixture was filtered, the residue washed with acetone. The combined acetone solution was then distilled and the residual oil crystallised from alcohol as a yellow solid of the *coumarone* (1.7 g.) giving a deep-red colouration with sulphuric acid. The mother liquor contained the uncyclised intermediate (VI) which was conveniently cyclised to give a further yield of the *coumarone* (0.8 g.) by stirring vigorously with 10% sodium hydroxide solution for one and half hrs.

The *coumarone*, purified by chromatography (Alumina: elution with benzene) crystallised from ethanol in yellowish prisms, m.p. 150-151°. (ν max. 1662 cm^{-1}). The N.M.R. spectrum showed $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$, at 7.47 τ , 30Me at 6.0-6.62 τ and 1 OMe 5.72 τ . (Found: C, 67.33; H, 5.81. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 67.40; H, 5.66%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid in red prisms, m.p. 204-205°. (Found: C, 58.60; H, 4.71. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_9\text{N}_4$ requires C, 58.21; H, 4.51%).

Bromination. A solution of the foregoing acetyl compound (1.0 g.) in boiling carbon tetrachloride (60 c.c.) was treated with N-Bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.). Benzoyl peroxide (30 mg.) was added to the mixture which irradiated with Hanovia lamp (500 watt) for 3 hrs. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solvent removed. The solid residue on crystallisation from alcohol gave possibly 5-bromo-2-acetyl-3-(3':4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxycoumarone, m.p. 206-207° (ν max. 1667 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 55.58; H, 4.50. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_6$ Br requires C, 55.16; H, 4.39%).

Ethyl 5:6-dimethoxy-2-veratrylphenoxyacetate (VII): A mixture of the phenol (V, 4.0 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (1.9 ml., excess), potassium carbonate (7.5 g.) in acetone (60 ml.) was refluxed for 8 hrs. On working up in the usual manner, the ester was left as a solid (5.0 g.) crystallising from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 97-98° (ν max 1755 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 62.37; H, 6.25. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 62.37; H, 5.98%).

Methyl 3-(3':4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxycoumarone-2-carboxylate: The foregoing ethyl ester (1.0 g.) was added to a methanolic solution of sodium methoxide (0.07 gm. sodium in dry methanol, 140 ml.) and the mixture refluxed on the water bath for 2 hrs. On cooling the *coumarone* separated (0.5 g.) which crystallised from methanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 148-49°. (ν max. 1710 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 64.15; H, 5.40. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 64.51; H, 5.41%).

On hydrolysis with methanolic sodium hydroxide, the corresponding acid (IX) was obtained, which crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 229-30° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.60; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 63.68; H, 5.06%).

3-(3':4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxycoumarone-2-acetic acid (XI): The foregoing acid (2.0 g.) was suspended in benzene (15 ml.) and converted into the acid chloride, by warming for 2 hrs. with oxalyl chloride. After removing the solvent and excess of oxalyl chloride in vacuum, the resulting acid chloride (m.p. 120-21°) was dissolved in dry ether (50 ml.) and added dropwise to an excess of ethereal diazomethane (from 10 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and the mixture left overnight. On removal of ether in vacuum, the resulting *diazoketone* was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 156-57° (decomp.). (ν max. 2118 cm^{-1}). (Found: N, 13.99. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.65%).

A solution of the diazoketone in dioxane (30 cc.) was added dropwise into a stirred mixture of 10% aqueous silver nitrate (20 ml.) in concentrated ammonium hydroxide (30 ml.) at 75°. After two and half hrs. the mixture was allowed to cool, filtered, diluted with water and extracted with chloroform 3-3':4'-*Dimethoxyphenyl*)-6:7-*dimethoxycoumarone-2-acetamide* (0.8 g.) left on removal of solvent crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colourless needles, m.p. 170-71°. (Found: C, 64.72; H, 5.97. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N$ requires C, 64.68; H, 5.70%).

The amide on hydrolysis by boiling with aqueous ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave the acetic acid which was isolated with ether. The acid failed to solidify.

The above crude (0.3 g.) was dissolved in benzene (20 ml.) and treated with phosphorus pentoxide (1.0 g.) and the mixture refluxed on the water bath for three and half hrs. The cooled mixture was then treated with iced water, extracted with ether and the organic layer freed from acid by repeatedly washing with sodium bicarbonate solution. On removal of solvent, a gum was obtained which was purified by chromatography over alumina. The product did not crystallise and a thin layer chromatography proved it to be homogeneous. The compound gave a positive ferric reaction and had i.r. absorption at 1740 cm^{-1} (thin film).

2'-*Ethoxycarbonyl-2-hydroxy-3:4:4':5'-tetramethoxybenzophenone* (XII). *m*-Hemipinic acid half ethyl ester (1 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by suspending it in benzene (5 ml.) and treating the suspension with oxalyl chloride (1 ml.) at the room temperature for 6 hrs. After removing all volatile matter at room temperature in vacuum, the resulting acid—a chloride was dissolved in dry ether (6 ml.) and added dropwise with exclusion of moisture, to an ice cold solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.9 g.) and trimethylpyrogallol (0.8 g.) in ether (8 ml.). The mixture was stirred for 1 hr. and left at the room temperature for 48 hrs. The mixture was then treated with iced hydrochloric acid and worked up in the usual manner to give the ester (2.0 g.) which crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 173-74° giving a red brown ferric reaction (ester band at 1708 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 61.68; H, 5.79. $C_{20}H_{22}O_8$ requires C, 61.53; H, 5.68%).

Hydrolysis of the ester (0.1 g.) with boiling 10% aqueous methanolic potassium hydroxide (6 ml.) gave 2'-carboxy-2-hydroxy-3:4:4':5'-tetramethoxybenzophenone (0.08 g.) which crystallised from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 190° (ν max. 1690 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 59.98; H, 5.30. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 59.66; H, 5.01%).

Haematoxylinic acid (XIII): A mixture of (XII, 4 g.) ethyl bromoacetate (3.5 ml) and acetone (50 ml.) was heated under reflux for 5 hrs. On working up ethyl haematoxylinic acid was obtained as a syrup which was hydrolysed by boiling with 10% aqueous methanolic caustic potash (40 ml.) during 1 hr. After removing methanol in vacuum, the residue was diluted with water (50 ml.) and acidified to give haematoxylinic acid (4 g.) which was collected after 24 hrs. The acid crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles, m.p. 180°. (lit.³ m.p. 180°) (ν max. 1700, 1720 cm^{-1}).

3-(2-*Carboxymethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl*)-6:7-*dimethoxycoumarone* (XV): A mixture of haematoxylinic acid (4.5 g.), potassium acetate (12 g.), acetic anhydride (45 ml.) was heated at 150° in an oil bath for 1 hr. cooled and treated with water (250 ml.). The precipitated 3-(2-*carboxy-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl*)-6:7-*dimethoxycoumarone* was collected and

crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow crystalline needles (2.6 g.) m.p. 178°. (ν max. 1690 cm^{-1}) (Found: C, 63.80; H, 5.20. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 63.68; H, 5.06%).

The *methyl ester* prepared by diazomethane crystallised from methanol in prisms, m.p. 118°. (ν max. 1690 cm^{-1} ester). (Found: C, 64.71; H, 5.53. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 64.51; H, 5.41%).

The above acid (2.5 g.) was converted into the acid chloride on treatment with thionyl chloride (1.2 ml.) in benzene (50 ml.) on boiling water bath for 1 hr. After evaporation of the reaction mixture in vacuum, the acid chloride was obtained as a viscous liquid which was dissolved in benzene (20 ml.) and added dropwise to ethereal diazomethane (from 10 g. nitrosomethylurea) at 0° and left overnight. Next day on working up the diazoketone was obtained as a solid, m.p. 152° (decomp.) (ν max. 2090 cm^{-1}). A solution of this compound in dioxan (25 ml.) was added during 10 minutes to a well stirred solution 10% silver nitrate (25 ml.) in concentrated ammonium hydroxide (15 ml.) at 70° and the mixture kept at this temperature for 3 hrs. From the filtered mixture, 3-(3-carbamylethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-6:7-dimethoxycoumarone was isolated with chloroform and crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, (1.2 g.), m.p. 171-73° (amide bands at 3360, 3480, 1617 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 64.78; H, 5.75; N, 3.92. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ requires C, 64.68; H, 5.70; N, 3.77%).

On hydrolysis with 10% aqueous methanolic potassium hydroxide (20 ml.) for 10 hrs. this amide gave rise to the corresponding *acid* (0.8 g.) which failed to solidify. The compound gave a deep red-colouration with sulphuric acid. (broad absorption at 1700 and 1720 cm^{-1}).

α -Anhydro-o-tetramethylhaematoxylone (II): The above crude acid (0.75 g.) was cyclised by means of concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml.) at the room temperature during half an hour and pouring the red mixture to ice (50 g.). α -Anhydro-o-tetramethylhaematoxylone was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates (0.4 g.), m.p. 208°, lit.^{3,4}, m.p. 202-206°, 208-210°. (OH absorptions at 3510 and 3395 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 67.81; H, 5.21. Calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$: C, 67.79; H, 5.12%). On warming with a little alcoholic potassium hydroxide containing a drop of chloroform, the compound gave an intense bluish green solution.

The acetate prepared by the action of acetic anhydride in pyridine solution crystallised from dilute acetic acid in cream coloured plates, m.p. 194°, undepressed on admixture with a synthetic specimen kindly provided by Prof. O. Dann. The infra-red spectra were also identical (ν max 1765 cm^{-1}).

The *benzoate* prepared by the action of benzoyl chloride in pyridine solution crystallised from alcohol in wooly needles, m.p. 174-75° (with darkening) (ν max. 1745 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 70.50; H, 4.75. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 70.73; H, 4.84%).

Oxidation to the quinone (IV). A solution of potassium nitrosodisulphonate (0.2 g.) in water (15 ml.) containing potassium dihydrogen phosphate (3 ml., 0.60 M) was added quickly to a solution of α -anhydro-o-tetramethylhaematoxylone (0.12 g.) in acetone (5 ml.) and the mixture left at the room temperature for 12 hrs. Acetone was removed under reduced pressure and the black prisms of the quinone (IV)

collected (0.04 g.), m.p. 298°. (ν max. 1640, 1650 cm^{-1}). Condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine in acetic acid gave the corresponding *quinazoline derivative* which crystallised from acetic acid in orange yellow needles, m.p. 284°. (Found: N, 6.40. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ requires N, 6.36%).

The authors wish to thank the authorities of Patna and Magadh University for the provision of a generous grant.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY, PATNA-5

Received, March 31, 1967.